

baby hand sprayer. Five hours after spraying, the seedlings were removed and the root portion washed.

The seedlings in test tubes with water were exposed for 24 h to GLH that had fed on RTV-infected plants for 4 d, at 2 insects/seedling. Fifty seedlings were inoculated per treatment.

Inoculated seedlings were

transplanted in pots in insect-proof cages for development of symptoms. A fresh seedling already treated with a plant product or chemical was introduced into each tube containing an insect. Survival of insects was recorded until all insects died.

Seed oils gave higher GLH mortality than leaf extracts (see table). Neem oil

gave the highest mortality. GLH mortality on leaf extract-treated seedlings was not significantly different from that on untreated seedlings.

Percentage RTV-infected seedlings was much reduced in all treatments over control. Seedlings treated with leaf extracts of nirgunda and bilwa had low RTV infection rates. □

Weed management

Chemical weed control in transplanted rice

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Two experiments, one in less weedy and one in highly weedy fields, evaluated five herbicides — piperophos + dime-thametryn, butachlor, chlornitrofen, thiobencarb, and pendimethalin — at the adaptive research farm and 5 farmers' fields in 1983. Chlornitrofen and piperophos + dimethametryn were

not used in the highly weedy trials. An unweeded check was maintained.

The experiments were laid out in completely randomized blocks with three replications. KS-282 rice variety seedlings were transplanted at 35-40 d in 10- × 6-m plots the last week of Jun. Butachlor mixed with 60 kg sand and other granular herbicides were broadcast; pendimethalin in 400 liters water/ha was sprayed 2-3 d after transplanting (DT). Water (4-5 cm deep) was retained in the fields for 5 d to allow herbicides to dissolve and make a

layer or film on the soil or water surface. Fertilization was 115 kg N, 25 kg P, and 47.3 kg K/ha. All the P and K and half the N were added at puddling, half the N at 30 DT. Weed count at 45 DT and at tillering (75 DT) was taken from 2 randomly selected 1-m² quadrats/plot. Yields were averaged.

Benefit-to-cost ratios were calculated by dividing the extra benefits attained from enhanced yield by the extra costs incurred for each treatment. Extra costs and benefits included cost and labor charges for herbicide application and price of enhanced yield.

Tillering was enhanced significantly by weed treatments except at the lower rate of butachlor in highly weedy fields (see table). The presence of grassy and more competitive weeds such as *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link, *E. crus-galli* (L.) Beauv. and *Paspalum distichum* L., resulted in significant yield losses. Weed control was not necessary when weed infestations were low. Weed control in rice can be economically achieved with chemical herbicides. Underdosing of butachlor is not beneficial.

In order of their prevalence, weeds in the experimental fields were *Cyperus iria* L., *C. difformis* L., *C. rotundus* L., *Fimbristylis miliacea* (L.) Vahl, *Echinochloa crus-galli* ssp. *hispidula* (Retz.) Honda, *Sphenoclea zeylanica* Gaertn., *E. colona*, *E. glabrescens* Munro ex Hook. f., *Marsilea minuta* L., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Paspalum distichum*, *Nymphaea nouchali* Burm. f., *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Willd., *Leptochloa chinensis* (L.) Nees, *Digitaria ciliaris* (Retz.) Koel., and *Trianthema portulacastrum* L. □

Effect of chemical weed control on tillering and yield of transplanted coarse rice and benefit-to-cost ratios of different weeding treatments in less and highly weedy fields.

Herbicide ^a	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Weed control ^b (no./m ²)	Tillering ^b (no./m ²)	Paddy yield ^b (t/ha)	Benefit:cost ^c
<i>Less weedy fields</i>					
Check	—	25.7	e 299.2 a	5.1 a	—
Piperophos + dimethametryn G	0.910	4.0	bc 328.7 ab	5.5 a	—
Butachlor EC	0.975	11.3	d 309.1 ab	5.1 a	—
Butachlor EC	1.200	2.0	a 340.0 b	5.6 a	—
Chlornitrofen G	3.600	15.5	d 305.5 ab	5.1 a	—
Thiobencarb G	2.000	6.0	c 327.3 ab	5.4 a	—
Thiobencarb G	2.500	3.0	ab 337.9 b	5.5 a	—
Pendimethalin EC	1.237	5.0	bc 334.0 ab	5.5 a	—
<i>Highly weedy fields</i>					
Check	—	164.3	e 215.6 a	5.3 a	—
Butachlor EC	0.975	72.0	d 226.2 a	5.6 a	1.82:1
Butachlor EC	1.200	11.7	a 285.6 c	7.5 d	9.79:1
Thiobencarb G	2.000	35.0	c 252.5 b	6.2 b	2.88:1
Thiobencarb G	2.500	22.3	bc 268.1 bc	7.0 c	4.40:1
Pendimethalin EC	1.237	15.3	ab 270.4 bc	7.0 c	4.33:1

^a G = granule, EC = emulsifiable concentrate. ^b Av of 6 sites and 3 replications at each site in the district. In a column, figures followed by a common letter are not statistically different at 0.05% level of confidence (DMRT). ^c For economic analysis, the costs included herbicide price (thiobencarb 10 G @ \$1.21/kg, and butachlor 60 EC and pendimethalin 33 EC @ \$8.62 and \$8.05/liter, respectively) and application costs (\$2.59 or \$1.44/spray or broadcast). Benefits included the price of enhanced yield over that of the check @ \$3.33/140 kg paddy.

Benefit:cost = $\frac{\text{extra benefits}}{\text{extra costs}}$ (for treatments).